

Review on Comparative Analysis of Heavy Metal Concentrations in River and Lake Waters: Implications for Water Quality and Human Health

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Abstract-

There are many different types of pollution, including soil, air, and water. Among these, water pollution is most hazardous since it can lead to severe health issues in living beings. The atomic weight of heavy metals ranges from 63.8 to 200.5, and their specific gravity is higher than 5. Heavy metal contamination is a major environmental concern in present scenario. Heavy metal must be eliminated from water to resolve this hazard. Most heavy metals are harmful to human health and environment, even in minimal amounts. Animals, humans and plants require water to sustain and thrive. Heavy metals are extremely poisonous, which makes them unfavorable to the surroundings. This review paper compares the concentration of heavy metals in various rivers, including the Ganga, Yamuna, Narmada, Kabini, Mahanadi, Kharun, and Ponds of Chhattisgarh (Vivekanand Sarovar and Maharaj Bandh Talab, based on their physical presence. The results are then compared to the maximum amount of water that is safe to drink. Pond and river water contain a variety of heavy metals, including Fe, Cu, Zn, Ni, Mn, Pb, As and Cr. Of these Pb, Cr, and Fe are dangerous if their concentrations exceed allowed levels. Water resources require removal of heavy metals from water since they possess a substantial threat.

Keywords- Heavy metals, water pollution, river water, lake water, toxic nature.

Introduction-

Water is most important and significant natural resource for the survival of the earth. 71% of the earth's surface is occupied by water. Ocean accommodate approximately 96.5% of the earth's water content, which is saline in nature. Only 1.7% of freshwater is in form of glaciers, rivers, lakes and ponds in the earth. Rivers serves as lifeline for all living things on earth. The main source of water on earth is rainwater. Rainwater is majorly accountable for recharge of river water^[1]. The quality of river water plays a major role for development of culture and economy and also in monitoring of environment^[2]. Ponds and lakes are other major water resources that significantly impact availability of fresh water. Lakes and ponds may be permanently linked to rivers or may be isolated water resources with inadequate drainage. The climate affects the temporary nature of some lakes and ponds^[3]. According to studies, ponds and lakes make up more than 90% of the 304 million standing water bodies on earth, or around 30% of all standing water by surface area^[4]. Unfortunately, these small aquatic systems are disregarded in almost all internationally significant perspectives and activities and are viewed as unrelated to global issues. The aquatic environment and the worldwide network of water sites are inherently accompanied by small bodies of water^[5]. The quality of river, pond or lake water can be affected by various factors like topography, geology, climate change, use of land for social causes and biological processes etc. Trace metals continue to exist as environmental pollutants in freshwater resources due to both natural and man-made causes.^[6] Since rivers are the primary source of freshwater spring recharge, most rivers that run through urban areas are at the top of the effluent discharge and, if left untreated and uncontrolled, can also contaminate the groundwater^[7]. Water resource systems are under pressure due to rapid urbanization and industrialization, which restricts the ability of economics and societies to expand sustainably^[8]. Watersheds are significantly impacted by high-intensity population growth, climate change, and water pollution^[11]. A wide range of specialists including hydrologists, engineers, ecologists, geologists and geomorphologists are concerned with challenges being faced by modern society^[12]. Heavy metals that contaminates in water bodies like rivers, ponds lakes etc. are pollute nature and have drawn attention in recent times^[7]. The elevated levels of heavy metals in water resources have detrimental effects on people, plants, and animals^[9,10] Heavy metals which are found in industrial effluents are absorbed by aquatic plants and also absorbed in sediments which is a factor for river water pollution^[12]. Urbanization, increased water demands from agriculture, and water supply contamination are the main causes of the shortage of water accessible for society and the environment^[13]. Raising awareness and encouraging implementers to take part in various government policies and programs can help reduce water pollution^[14]. According to drinking water standard of water in the presence of heavy metals given by WHO is given in Table 1-

Table 1- Heavy metals permissible limits in drinking water^[28] –

S.No	Heavy metals	Permissible limits according to WHO	Unit
1.	Fe	0.1	Mg/l
2.	Cu	1.0	Mg/l
3.	Hg	0.001	Mg/l
4.	Cd	0.005	Mg/l
5.	As	0.05	Mg/l
6.	Pb	0.05	Mg/l
7.	Zn	5.0	Mg/l
8.	Cr	0.1	Mg/l

WHO- World Health Organization

In this present study, we try to arrange the data from the various riverine flows in the India that are very important and similarly, some ponds that equally indicate the environmental pollution.

Sources of heavy metals and effects

Sources

Industrial processes like mining, farming, and tanneries are typically responsible for disposing of heavy metals. Industrial effluent are major contributor of chemicals like Pb, Cr, Hg, As, Cu, etc. in water resources [25]. Heavy metals are poisonous for both humans and plants if their concentration rises to a hazardous level [47]. Water bodies have been contaminated by metals such as Cr due to the steel and textile industries [15]. Electroplating, zinc base casting, and silver refinery effluents are the source of nickel entry in water bodies [16]. Batteries, car paints, steel, and mining industry release Pb into waterways. Through the use of pesticides, fertilizers, and refineries, Hg can also find its way into water bodies [17]. Copper water heaters, alcoholic beverages, and fungicides are some of the ways that Cu can also enters into water bodies [18]. Heavy metals like Mn, Cr, Ni, Fe, and Zn when become excess in water bodies affect the health of aquatic creatures, hence monitoring of heavy metal deposition is necessary for public health [19]. Excess presence of heavy metals like Cu, Fe, and Zn highly lethal for humans as well as animals [20].

Fig. 1- Source of heavy metals

Table 2-Heavy metals and their effects in humans^[21-22]

S.No	Heavy metal	Effects
1.	As	High levels of toxicity, causing harm to several organs, and Carcinogenic properties in humans.
2.	Cr	Respiratory problems, pulmonary fibrosis, lung cancer.
3.	Cu	Mental disorder, heart problem, hypertension.
4.	Fe	Overabundance susceptibility to cardiovascular diseases.
5.	Mn	Neurological disorder.
6.	Ni	Dermatitis, chest pain, encephalopathy.
7.	Pb	Birth defects, cerebral palsy.
8.	Zn	Damage of nervous membrane, the corrosive effect of skin.
9.	Hg	The liver function increases due to Hg exposure, which affects child growth.
10.	Cd	Cancer, basal breast tumours, bone defects

Fig 2- Release of heavy metals on water resources^[21]

The Ganga river

In India river Ganga is regarded as a goddess, the holy river, because of its abundance of water throughout the year Ganga contributes a significant role to the development of the Indian economy and civilization ^[23,26]. In spite of the river's respect, its condition is continuously deteriorating by the heavy industrial disposal, sewage effluents and other anthropogenic activities^[24] From the origin the holy river Ganga covers 2550 km of area, which is approx 25% of Indian water resources ^[25]. In the Kanpur area, where approximately 1000 MLD of toxic effluents from about 400 tanneries, municipal waste, and industrially polluted Ponda River discharge their waste to the river Ganga^[25]. Ganga River upstream at Haridwar in the year 2020 average concentration of heavy metals is given in Table -3^[27].

Table 3- Concentration of heavy metals in Ganga River at different locations^[27]

River Location	As	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn	Unit	References
Ganga river Upstream at Haridwar (Site 1)	0.00235	0.063	0.141	0.315	0.0532	0.0105	0.144	0.148	Mg/l	Subuddhi et al (2023)
Ganga river Upstream at Haridwar (Site 2)	0.001	0.126	0.139	0.342	0.0614	0.0226	0.105	0.21	Mg/l	Subuddhi et al (2023)

Fig.3- Locations of Ganga fluvial system^[28]

Status of heavy metals in the Ganga River-

The average concentration of heavy metals in the Ganga River upstream at Haridwar in the year 2020 (site 1) for As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Pb and Zn are 0.00235 mg/l, 0.063 mg/l, 0.141 mg/l, 0.315 mg/l, 0.144 mg/l, and 0.148 mg/l respectively, and for (site 2) is 0.001 mg/l, 0.126 mg/l, 0.139 mg/l, 0.342mg/l, 0.105 mg/l, 0.21 mg/l respectively^[27]. The amount Of Fe and Pb is higher than the permissible limits of drinking water^[28]. According to a study on the river Ganga in Bangladesh, surface overflow and heavy rainfall during the monsoon and post-monsoon seasons resulted in the highest concentration of heavy metals^[29]. According to Maura et al. (2019), the Ganga River water in Varanasi had concentrations of Cd, Pb, and Cr of 0.85 mg/l, 0.24 mg/l, and 0.45 mg/l^[30]. Due to severe pollution, the river's colour has changed from blue to blackish between Farrukhabad and Kanpur^[31]. The Ganga River in Parshuram Ghat Haridwar, Uttarakhand is polluted due to the presence of Fe, Pb, Mn, and Cd higher than permissible limit^[32].

Fig- 4 [A] Shri Parshuram Ghat, at Haridwar^[32] 4[B] Polluted site in ghat of Ganga river^[32] 4 [C] Ganga river polluted bottom^[32]

The Yamuna river

River Yamuna is a sacred river of Northern India. It originates from the lower Himalaya Yamunotri glaciers, which are about 6387 meters above sea level. Yamuna River is the largest tributary of the river Ganga^[33].

Fig 5- Locations of Yamuna river^[41]

The Yamuna River is contaminated by municipal sewage waste and other man-made activities^[34]. 22 sewers in Delhi alone submerge into the Yamuna River (Dhillon et al. 2013). The Yamuna River has alarming concentrations of heavy metals from household, industrial trash and pesticides that seep from agricultural land^[35]. Heavy metals like Fe, Zn, Ni, Cd and Pb are also present in excess of permitted levels in all water samples, which contributes to the river's pollution^[36,40]. The Yamuna River runs about 22 km from Palla to Okhla in Delhi^[37]. The 22 km radius around this place is the most polluted area of Delhi^[38,39]. According to the ICMR, CPCB,

WHO, and EPA reports, Cr at the Yamuna River, Delhi exceeds the permissible limits^[34]. Table no 4 shows the concentration of heavy metals present in Yamuna.

Table 4- Concentrations of heavy metals in river Yamuna at different locations^[34,37]

River Location	Cr	Cu	Fe	Ni	Pb	Zn	Cd	Unit	References
Delhi- Nizammudin Bridge	0.08	0.06	-	0.32	0.030	0.133	0.061	Mg/l	Singh et al (2014)
Delhi- stretch(Palla to Okhla)	0.068	0.144	1.451	0.096	0.084	0.412	-	Mg/l	Kumar et al (2023)

Status of heavy metals in the Yamuna River

River Yamuna at Delhi- stretch(Palla to Okhla) has concentration of Fe and pb is 1.451 mg/L and 0.084mg/l which is higher than their standard limit of 0.1 mg/L, and 0.05 mg/l respectively^[37]. The presence of Fe in water has an impact on human health, causing conditions such as neurotoxicity and carcinogenicity^[41,42]. Delhi- Nizammudin Bridge which is another location point for river Yamuna has a high concentration of Cd is 0.061 mg/l which is higher than their standard limit that is 0.005 mg/l^[34]. River Yamuna at Allahabad in the study of six sample sites concentration of Zn and Pb is higher than the maximum acceptable limits ^[43]. Yamuna Nagar (upper division) famous for paper and sugar production that is discharge harmful chemicals into Yamuna River , as well as in Agra region high HPI (heavy metal pollution index) is being observed ^[44,45]. Due to this reason Yamuna River is polluted with heavy metals and is not safe for drinking purpose ^[44].

The Narmada river

The Narmada is the sacred river of Madhya Pradesh. Ganga, Yamuna, and Narmada among the many other water bodies are revered in Indian culture^[46]. In M.P., the Narmada River is the lifeline, that extends 85,938 km from east to west of the boundary of M.P. ^[47].

Fig.6 – Locations of Narmada Basin^[54]

As a result of industrial activity and heavy metals, the Narmada River is unfit for human consumption^[48-49], Different types of heavy metals like Cu, Fe, Mn etc are found in River Narmada,^[50,51]. Forests, agriculture, and mining activities predominate in the upper Narmada watershed. As a result, the river gets flow with untreated urban wastewater, woods, and agriculture waste^[53]. The amount of Fe in the River Narmada at Hoshangabad is found to be greater than the WHO limit^[54]. The concentration of heavy metals in the Narmada River at different locations is given in Table 5-

Table 5-Concentration of heavy metals in Narmada River at different locations^[46,54]

River Location	As	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn	Unit	References
Narmada river Amarkantak to Koteshwar (M.P.)	0.0006	0.00262	0.0808	0.5595	0.01368	0.00168	0.00881	0.2217	Mg/l	Mishra et al (2021)
Narmada river Hoshangabad (M.P.)	0.00107	0.11106	0.0067	0.21	-	0.00154	0.004	6*10 ⁻⁵	Mg/l	Hussain et al (2014)

Status of heavy metals in the Narmada River

Heavy metals release in river Narmada by anthropogenic activities, Mn and Zn detected in all sample sites of river Narmada, due to their high-level carcinogen raises a serious problem in humans^[52]. In observation, it is found that in the upper part of Narmada river (Amarkantak to Jabalpur), Heavy metals such as Cr, Mn, Cu, and Pb are present in sediment samples at different concentrations^[53]. Narmada River at Hoshangabad, Mandleshwar, and Garudeshwar has been polluted due to municipal sewage and industrial discharge and it is the source of heavy metals like Cu, Cr, and Fe^[54]. The amount of Fe among other heavy metals is 0.5595 mg/l in Amarkantak, which is higher than the WHO limit that is 0.1 mg/l and it is harmful to plants and animals^[28,46]. Another location of river Narmada is Hoshangabad (M.P.), in which Amount of Fe and Cr is observe 0.21 mg/l and 0.11106 mg/l respectively, which is high according to the standard limit of WHO^[28,54].

The Kabini river

In the Wayanad region of Kerala, India, the Kabini River, a significant tributary of the Cauvery River, forms the Kuruva River island system and originates from the Western Ghats of Wayanad district Kerala^[95]. The Kabini River also travel through Nanjangud, an industrial area and Byalaru village of Karnataka. it is contaminated with Cu, Cr, Mn, Fe, Pb, Ni, and Zn^[55]. The river Kabini is heavily contaminated as a result of the textile, paper, leather, pharmaceutical, and electronic industries in the Nanjangud industrial region in Mysore district, Karnataka^[56].

Multidisciplinary Scientific Reviewer | Half Yearly | Volume-05 | Issue-01 | Jan - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Location-map-of-Kabini-river-watershed_fig1_350628107

Fig 7 – Locations of Kabini River^[81]

The concentration of heavy metals in the Kabini River at different locations is given in Table 6-

Table 6- Concentration of heavy metals in Kabini River at different locations^[55]

River Location	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Zn	Unit	References
Nanjangund	30.06	20.06	51.43	25.77	65.26	Mg/l	Hejabi et al (2011)
Byalaru	26.43	27.93	38.9	35.7	57.66	Mg/l	Hejabi et al (2011)

Status of heavy metals in the Kabini River

Kabini River in Karnataka in the Mysore district was recorded as highly polluted river with heavy metals, which is due to the presence of lethal heavy metals in the river basin and man-made activities^[56,57]. In Kabini River Nanjangund area, mean concentration of heavy metals like Cu, Cr, Zn, Fe and Mn is 20.06mg/l, 30.06 mg/l, 65.26 mg/l, 51.43mg/l and 25.77mg/l and for Byalaru area it is 27.93 mg/l, 26.43 mg/l, 57.66 mg/l, 38.9 mg/l, and 35.7 mg/l respectively which is extremely higher than standard limit of WHO^[28,55].

The Mahanadi river

In the Indian peninsula, the Mahanadi River is one of the main interstate east-flowing rivers. Water from the river is used for industrial, residential, and agricultural uses. ^[58].About 13 kilometres above Sheorinarayan, in the Bilaspur District, the first significant tributary, Seonath, meets the Mahanadi. The Hirakund Dam, which is 10 km from Sambalpur City on the other side of Mahanadi, has rocky beds where the river water flows^[59]. The predominant part of dissolved metals at the Mahanadi River is due to several industrial and urban pollutants^[58].

Fig 8- Location Map of Mahanadi and tributaries^[58]

The Bay of Bengal receives 18.216×10^3 t of total heavy metals from the Mahanadi River, while the basin's estimated rate of erosion is $128.645 \text{ kg km}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ ^[60]. The mean and average concentration of heavy metals in the states of Odisha and Chhattisgarh is given in Table 7-

Table 7 - Concentration of heavy metals in Mahanadi River at different locations^[58]

River Location	As	Cr	Cu	Fe	Hg	Ni	Pb	Zn	Cd	Unit	References
Mahanadi Rajim (Chhattisgarh)	0.0023	0.0102	0.02441	1.06567	0.00065	0.02488	0.00569	0.02596	0.000148	Mg/l	Hussian et al (2020)
Mahanadi Tikrapara (Odisha)	0.00263	0.00538	0.00933	0.63467	0.0004	0.01021	0.0063	0.28187	0.000280	Mg/l	Hussian et al (2020)

Status of heavy metals in Mahanadi River

River pollution is primarily caused by presence of toxic heavy metals in river catchment zones. The findings show that this water is not appropriate for agricultural or household use ^[61]. Heavy metals concentration Mahanadi Rajim in (Chhattisgarh) and Mahanadi Tikrapara in(Odisha) when compare with the permissible limit of drinking water it is observed that the concentration of As, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn, Cd is 0.0023 mg/l, 0.01028 mg/l, 0.02441 mg/l, 1.06567 mg/l, 0.00065 mg/l, 0.02488 mg/l, 0.00569mg/l, 0.02596 mg/l, 0.000148 mg/l^[58], and for Odisha that is 0.00263 mg/l, 0.00538 mg/l, 0.00933 mg/l, 0.63467 mg/l, 0.0004 mg/l, 0.01021 mg/l, 0.0063 mg/l, 0.28187 mg/l, 0.000280 mg/l respectively^[58]. Finally it is find, that the concentration of Fe in the river water of Mahanadi Rajim (Chhattisgarh) and Mahanadi Tikrapara (Odisha) is greater than the permissible of drinking water standard^[58,28].

The Kharun river

The Kharun River is a perennial river that originates southeast Balod Tehsil of the Durg (C.G.)^[62]. The growing population of coastal cities and the continuous expansion of industry and agricultural have an impact on pollution in the Kharun River^[63]. Several locations close to Raipur, including Bhathagaon Anicut, Mahadev Ghat, Kathadih, Raipura, Sarena, and others, have eight major sewerage outlets that discharge sewage straight into Kharun^[92]. The Kharun River flows 2.2 kilometers from the Siltara industrial area, which is about 10 kilometers from Raipur city^[64].

Fig 9- Location Map of Kharun^[96]

Heavy metal concentration in river Kharun (Chhattisgarh) at different locations is given in Table 8-

Table 8- Concentration of heavy metals in Kharun River at different locations^{[62, 64] -}

River Location	Cr	Fe	Mn	Pb	Zn	Unit	References
Khraun River (Raipur) C.G.	0.7520	0.0736	0.0746	0.1715	1.2361	Mg/l	Kumar et al (2023)
Khraun River (Siltara Industrial site) C.G.	0.642	0.498	0.3	0.811	0.326	Mg/l	Manoj Kumar Tiwari (2016)

Fig 10- Locations of Kharun river at Siltara industrial Area [64]

Status of heavy metals in Kharun River

The quality of surface water bodies has drastically decreased as a result of industrial effluent and residential trash [62]. The river contamination has had a negative health impact on the village and the urban residents [89]. It is found that Kharun River is hively polluted due to the presence of heavy metals like Cr, Pb, and Fe. According to Kumar et al (2023) the concentration of metals in Raipur city and Siltara industrial area is 0.7520mg/l, 0.1715mg/l, and 0.0736mg/l, and 0.642mg/l, 0.811mg/l, and 0.498 mg/l respectively [62, 64]. It is higher than the permissible limit of drinking water for Cr and Pb is 0.1 mg/l and 0.05 mg/l respectively [28].

Ponds of Chhattisgarh

India's water bodies have a rich sociocultural past. Ponds (johads, taalab), and lakes (taal) use for irrigation, drinking water supply, residential use, and tourism/culture [65]. In this paper we have selected two ponds of Raipur (C.G.) and will explain ponds heavy metal contamination.

Vivekanada Sarovar, Raipur (C.G.)

Raipur is known for its pond. In the year of 1977, there were approximately 70 ponds in the capital area of Chhattisgarh^[94], Vivekananda Sarovar is Raipur's largest pond, built during the reign of Budheswardeva in the 17th century^[65]. Thick, dense habitation envelops Vivekananda Sarovar. Therefore, human influence affects the water's physico-chemical and biological properties^[94].

Fig 11 – Location of Vivekanand Sarovar Raipur(C.G.)^[93]

Maharaj Bandh Talab

Maharaj Bandh Talab was established in the 18th century to irrigate farmlands and serve the local population. These days, the local community uses it on a daily basis. Additionally, some people use its water for irrigation and cattle^[65]. The primary causes of contamination in pond sediments are fertilizer and pesticide^[67]. The uses of pond water in agricultural regions and runoff from near by household localities sewage without any proper infrastructure are main cause of water pollution^[67].

Fig 12- Maharaj Bandh Talab Raipur (C.G)^[68]

Fig 13- Base map of Raipur city showing the position of Vivekanand Sarovar (Budha Talab) and Maharaj Bandh Talab^[65]

The concentration of heavy metals in Vivekananda Sarovar and Maharaj Bandh Talab is given in Table 9-

Table 9- Concentration of heavy metals in Vivekananda Sarovar and Maharaj Bandh Talab Raipur (C.G.)^[67]

Pond location	Cu	Fe	Mn	Cd	Co	Zn	Unit	References
Vivekanand Sarovar	0.0065	0.24	0.28277	0.00002	0.00032	0.09867	Mg/l	Dash et al (2022)
Maharaj Bandh Talab	0.0056	0.40	0.53176	0.00013	0.00049	0.05911	Mg/l	Dash et al (2022)

Status of heavy metals in Vivekanand Sarovar and Maharaj Bandh Talab Raipur (C.G.)

Anthropogenic sources of heavy metal pollution in aquatic environments include the burning of fossil fuels, sewage and industrial wastewater discharges, and air deposition [66]. In a study of heavy metal pollution in Vivekanand Sarovar Raipur(C.G), it is found that amounts of Fe, Zn, Cu, and Cd are 0.24 mg/l, 0.09867 mg/l, 0.0065 mg/l, 0.00002mg/l and it is 0.40mg/l, 0.05911mg/l, 0.0056mg/l, 0.00013 mg/l respectively in Maharaj Bandh Talab Raipur (C.G.)^[67], the level of Fe in both ponds exceeds the WHO guideline limit for drinking water^[28].

Strategies to improve the heavy metal pollution of River Ganga, Yamuna, Narmada, Kabini, Mahanadi River, Kharun River, and Pond of Chhattisgarh (Budha Talab & Maharaj Bandh Talab) -

The strain of growing populations and industry is the main cause of river pollution. River cleanup was the primary goal of the Ganga Action Plan (GAP), which was created in 1985 to address this problem^[69]. On July 10, 2014, the Indian government launched the Namami Gange Programme (NGP) with the intention of employing eco-friendly techniques to clean up the Ganga River basin^[28]. Initiatives to purify the water of the Ganga River include the National Ganga River Basin Authority (NGRBA) and the Ganga River Basin Management Plan (GRBMP)^[70]. The Ganga Action Plan (GAP) and BIS recommendations are suitable for sustaining wastewater treatment when the Ganga river effluent discharge parameters exceed the widely recognized standard limits. Additionally, industrial waste must to undergo treatment prior to being discharged into water resources^[71], at 1985, the Ganga Action Plan called for the construction of gas or electric crematoriums, especially at places of religion, in Varanasi and Allahabad^[72]. In order to preserve and clean the Yamuna River, the government has implemented a number of programs and adhered to the Yamuna Action Plan (YAP)^[73]. Water pollution levels at various locations are developed and tracked by the Central Water Commission (CWC)^[74]. Additionally, Yamuna action projects YAP (II) and YAP (III) are being built. The Delhi stretch is the focus of YAP (III), which aims to lower Yamuna pollution^[75]. The new wastewater facility at Okhla (124 MGD) can reduce the pollutant load by 283 kg/MGD of wastewater at a cost of Rs300 crores, according to the study^[75,76]. Clean River water enhancement is gain by the implementation of rejuvenation strategies and ongoing monitoring of them^[77,78]. A suitable, river health monitoring campaign is conduct in the Narmada^[79]. According to the study of Kori et al, the Narmada River's east section is pollution-free, which is beneficial for aquatic life^[80]. Aamarkantak to Hoshangabad, Madhya Pradesh, is the upper portion of the Narmada River. The water is treated prior to use^[82]. In May 2017, the Madhya

Pradesh government in India suggested giving the Narmada "living being" entity status in order to fight pollution^[83]. A wastewater treatment plant is developed for the protection of Kabini River water^[84]. To avoid pollution in rivers continuous monitoring of river water is done, and contamination of heavy metals is also avoided in groundwater by leaching of heavy metals in soil in this way river is also protected from contamination of heavy metals^[85]. A major irrigation project in Mahanadi (Chhattisgarh) will include the construction of five dams: Ravishkar Sagar Dam, Dudhawa Dam, Murrumsili Dam, Sondur Dam, and Pairi Dam. Of these five dams, the first four have been completed, and the Pairi dam is now under construction^[86]. Industries in Chhattisgarh have started to demand that the fluids from the Mahanadi's original position be utilized to their maximum capacity^[87]. S. Jaiswal et al. (2009) investigated and evaluated the sedimentation of the Ravishankar Sagar (RSS) reservoir in the Mahanadi River Basin catchment area^[88]. Untreated industrial waste and water utilized in various operations are released into freshwater bodies and land systems, posing a serious hazard to the environment and human population^[90,91]. Kharun Riverfront Development Project (KRDP) is in its first phase which was developed with a cost of 2000 crores Rs in 20 km of river stretch to stop the construction of a dam to maintain an adequate amount of water and reuse of water at different purposes. It is based on Sabarmati projects to divert Kharun river water into Ravishankar Sagar dam^[92]. Adopting a thorough rejuvenation and conservation approach requires long-term monitoring of the trophic activity and water quality of urban ponds^[66]. The physical and chemical characteristics of pond water are monitored spatially, which aids in predicting, identifying, and evaluating the urban ponds' natural state and relationship to the environment. It also aids in the adoption of rejuvenation techniques^[93].

Comparison of various heavy metals in various rivers and ponds

Comparison between contamination of heavy metals in river Ganga, Yamuna, Narmada, Kabini, Mahanadi, Kharun, and ponds Vivekananda Sarovar and Maharaj Bandh Talab Raipur (C.G.) is given in Table 10 –

Table 10- Comparison of various heavy metals contamination in (mg/l) in various rivers and ponds-

S. N.	River / Pond	Location	As	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn	Hg	Cd	Co	References
1	Ganga River	Upstream at Haridwar (Site 1)	0.0235	0.063	0.141	0.315	0.0532	0.0105	0.144	0.148				Subuddhi et al(2023)
2	Ganga River	Upstream at Haridwar (Site 2)	0.001	0.126	0.139	0.342	0.0614	0.0226	0.105	0.21				Subuddhi et al (2023)
3.	Yamuna River	DelhiNizamuddin Bridge	-	0.08	0.06	-	-	0.32	0.30	0.133	-	0.061		Singh et al (2014)
4.	Yamuna River	Delhi stretch(Palla to Okhla)	-	0.068	0.144	1.451	-	0.096	0.084	0.412	-	-		Kumar et al (2023)
5.	Narmada River	Amarkantak to Koteswar (M.P.)	0.006	0.00262	0.0808	0.5595	0.01368	0.00168	0.00881	0.2217				Mishra et al (2021)
6.	Narmada River	Hoshangabad	0.00107	0.0067	0.067	0.21	-	0.00154	0.004	6*10 ⁻⁵	-	-	-	Hussian et al (2014)
7.	Kabini River Karnataka	Nanjangund	-	30.6	20.06	51.43	25.77	-	-	65.26	-	-	-	Hejabi et al (2011)
8.	Kabini River Karnataka	Byalaru	-	26.43	27.93	38.9	35.7	-	-	57.66	-	-	-	Hejabi et al (2011)
9.	Mahanadi River	Rajim (Chhattisgarh)	0.023	0.0102	0.2441	1.06567	-	0.02488	0.00569	0.02596	0.00065	0.000148	-	Hussian et al (2020)
10.	Mahanadi River	Tikrapara (Odisha)	0.0263	0.00538	0.00933	0.63467	-	0.01021	0.0063	0.2818	0.0004	0.000280		Hussian et al (2020)
11.	Khraun River	Raipur (C.G.)	-	0.7520	-	0.0736	0.0746	-	0.1715	1.2361	-	-	-	Kumar et al (2023)
12.	Khraun River	Siltara Industrial site (C.G).	-	0.642	-	0.498	0.3	-	0.811	0.326	-	-	-	Manoj Kumar Tiwari (2016)
13.	Vivekanand Sarovar	Raipur (C.G.)	-	-	0.0065	0.24	0.2877	-	-	0.09867	-	0.00002	0.00032	Dash et al (2022)

14.	Maharaj Bandh Talab	Raipur (C.G.)	-	-	0.00 56	0.40	0.5317 6	-	-	0.0591	-	0.0001 3	0.0 591	Dash et al (2022)
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Based on available data, the Narmada River in Madhya Pradesh has very low levels of arsenic pollution (0.0006 mg/l), while the Mahanadi River in the central Indian area of Tikrapara (Odisha) has the highest levels (0.0026 mg/l). according to Hejabi et al. Copper and chromium levels in the Kabini River are 20.06, 27.93 mg/l, and 30.6, 26.43 mg/l, respectively. A research by Hussian et al. found that the water of the Narmada River has the lowest amount of iron (0.21 mg/l). The concentration of nickel in the Yamuna River is 0.32 mg/l, more than that of comparable rivers. With a amount of 0.811 mg/l, the Kharun River (Siltara Industrial site) near Chhattisgarh has more lead pollution than other rivers. Compared to other rivers, the Kabini River in the Nanjangund industrial sector has a higher quantity of zinc (65.26 mg/l). Compared to other rivers and ponds, the water of the Yamuna River contains a higher quantity of cadmium, according to Singh et al. The amount of cobalt in Maharaj Bandh Talab Raipur is high as compare to Vivekanand Sarovar Pond in Raipur, which is 0.0591 mg/l. The River Kabini (Karnataka) is substantially more polluted than other rivers and ponds, as seen in Table 10 data.

Conclusion-

This review article summary about comparison of heavy metals concentration in river water like Ganga, Yamuna, Narmada, Kabini, Mahanadi, and Kharun rivers and ponds of Chhattisgarh Budha Talab, and Maharaj Bandh Talab and their acceptable limits of heavy metals in drinking water as WHO limits. The levels of various heavy metal contamination in rivers and ponds have been found higher than the WHO's recommended guidelines for safe drinking water. As these cause a number of negative health effects. hence, in order to prevent unforeseen health hazards, it is recommended that river water must be treated before being used for drinking. This study offers guidance for the future to scientists, conservationists, planners and administrators of water resources to take the appropriate steps to preserve the rivers' aesthetic value.

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